

ADDITIVE PRODUCTION PROCESSES FOR THE MANUFACTURING OF CUSTOMISED BIO-BASED PACKAGING

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Abstract: *Potential solutions by using additive manufacturing processes for customised bio-based packaging will be introduced. Two processes will be applied, fused filament fabrication (FFF) and binder jetting (3DP), both in combination with nearly entirely bio-based material systems. The focus is on individual packaging, as a representative of components with a defined short service life, which currently generate high unit costs for small to medium quantities. The biobased materials consist on the one hand of biobased polymers or binders, and on the other hand of renewable raw materials with residual character. These material combinations have not yet been used in additive manufacturing processes and offer enormous application potential through upcycling.*

Keywords: packaging, 3D printing, binder jetting, 3DP, FFF, residues, bio-based

1 INTRODUCTION

Packaging of goods usually consists of an outer packaging (e.g. cardboard) and an insert adapted to the component. These so-called interior fittings of packaging are either made of plastic - mostly polystyrene or polyethylene - or cardboard. There is both an economic and ecological desire for one-component packaging, i.e. outer packaging and interior fittings are made of the

same recyclable or biodegradable material. On the one hand, polystyrene should be avoided from a purely economic point of view, as it leads to higher costs in multi-component packaging and makes disposal more difficult. Added to this is the poor life cycle assessment of the plastic. For paper or cardboard interiors, which would allow single-component packaging, there are currently a number of manufacturing options, but these are geometrically limited and involve either large amounts of waste or expensive tools, see Figure 1.

Figure 1: Production possibilities of interior furnishings from paper/cardboard/carton

For these manufacturing with ecological materials the tooling costs of up to 6,000 € for fibre casting tools are enormous. Due to that tool costs, fibre casting is not economical for small quantities (< 1,000 pieces). For stamping the material input is high through wastage. Both types of production are also very limited in the variety of shapes of the parts.

For these reasons, plastics have been used up to now for lack of economic alternatives, for which there are several suitable manufacturing processes. If the required number of pieces is high, packaging is produced using the plastic injection moulding process. In this process, a plastic is liquefied (plasticised) and pressed into a mould with the help of pressure. After solidification, the part can be removed. The cost of injection moulds is very high at several 10,000 € and the process is designed for mass production (> 50,000 pieces)

where it is very profitable. For smaller quantities it is not economically due to the enormous costs for the tools. In addition, there are higher costs due to the Packaging Act³. Another possibility is the cutting of inserts from plastic foam. Again, the main reason for this choice is the lack of availability of cost-effective manufacturing technologies for bio-based and biodegradable materials. Figure 2 below shows two examples of plastic interiors that currently cannot be economically produced from cardboard using the processes mentioned in Figure 1.

Figure 2: Examples of plastic interiors

In order to meet the requirements of the German Packaging Act as well as to cost-effectively produce small quantities of complex packaging geometries, the use of additive manufacturing processes is a promising approach (Zeidler et al., 2018).

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Leftover paper dust from existing packaging processes is used as residual material in both processes, 3DP and FFF. Hausner number as well as Carr index determined with the characterised densities. Furthermore, the measured flowability with a ring shear tester shown in Table (EN ISO 3953, EN ISO 60, ASTM D6773-16).

³ The German Packaging Act (VerpackG) transposes the European Packaging Directive 94/62/EC into German law. It regulates the placing of packaging on the market as well as the return and high-quality recycling of packaging waste.

Table 1: Determined densities and values for the flowability

	Value	Classification
Solid density [g/cm³]	1.62	
Bulk density [g/cm³]	0.25	
Tap density [g/cm³]	0.34	
Hausner number [-]	1.33	reduced flowability
Carr index [%]	24.64	acceptable flowability
Flowability at FP 0 [-]	1.73	very cohesive – not flowable

The particle size distribution is shown in Figure 3. A sphericity of 0.74 approximates a cubic form of the particles.

Figure 3: Particel size distribution

Different types of commercially available resin systems based on chemical modified rosin acids developed by Robert Kraemer GmbH & Co. KG are used as binders in 3DP and as an additive in FFF.

Figure 4: Rosin as bio-based raw material (before chemical modification)

Initial results and methods are presented using three rosin resin types, each of which is 100% bio-based. In fused filament fabrication, the liquid resin PP 7330 is compounded into PLA 4043D as an additive. In Binder Jetting (3DP), the solid resins RK 3087 and RK 7065 are used as binders. The resins used for binder jetting were ground to the required fineness ($< 180 \mu\text{m}$). This was done in a vibrating disk mill. In this way, 100 g could be ground in batches of 10 seconds. The fine fraction ($w = 180 \mu\text{m}$) was then sieved off and fresh material was added.

2. 2 Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF)

Inspired by the excellent results regarding the mechanical properties and compatibility of modified rosin resins with PLA as matrix in injection moulding applications (Buschbeck et al., 2020), first preliminary tests of this material combination for filament production were tested. A novel resin type PP 7330 was compounded with 5% as additive in PLA 4043D on a twin screw extruder ZSC 25 from Noris Plastic GmbH & Co and filament with diameter 2,85 mm was fabricated on a High Speed High Precision Filament Line of Labtech Engineering Co.. Test specimens were printed from the filament on an Ultimaker S5 (cf. Figure 3, left-hand side) and injected from the compound on the Arburg Allrounder 370A as a benchmark. The first results are shown in Figure 5, right hand-side.

Figure 5: Printing of test specimens (left-hand side) and results of mechanical testing of printed and injected test specimens (right-hand side)

2. 3 Binder Jetting (3DP)

Binder jetting is an ink-based powder bed printing process. The applied powder consists of 85% matrix material (paper dust) and 15% binder powder (several biobased resins). A solution of 50% water and 50% ethanol is used as ink. The resins are locally and temporarily dissolved by the alcohol and thus glue the paper fibres to each other, cf. figure 6 (right). Samples are produced on the 3D-Printer ZCorp 310 by Z Corporation. As test specimens, five cubes each with an edge length of 20 mm and cylinders with diameter and height of 20 mm are produced using the following print settings: layer height 0.1 mm, saturation 140%. After printing, the parts are dried at 60 °C until a constant mass is reached.

Figure 6: Printing process (left), printed part (middle), microscope image of printed part at 200x zoom(right)

The printed specimens have sufficient accuracy with a percentage deviation of 0.5%. Furthermore, a compressive strength of $1.91 \pm 0.33 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (RK 3087) and $1.41 \pm 0.36 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (RK 7065) was achieved. Density of the printed parts is 0.24 g/cm^3 and therefore a porosity over 85%.

3 CONCLUSION

Using paper fibres as dust for additive manufacturing is a sustainable idea. It could be proven that this residual material fulfils the requirements for an FFF filler as well as for a matrix material in binder jetting (Jerman et al., 2020). First printing results could be presented with selected resins. The strength achieved in binder jetting is far above that of polysterol. In addition, the porosity is high and a high damping capacity can be assumed. An application as packaging inlay is therefore recommendable. To validate this, further studies on solubility and damping behaviour are planned. Using FFF, the PLA 4043D was made processable by adding PP 7330. The obtained Young's modulus property loss of 10% compared to the injection molded samples was expected due to the different processes. In a next step, the filler content of the paper dust residues will be increased up to 30% and the properties will be investigated in combination with the resins from Robert Kraemer GmbH & Co. KG. A demonstration part of mentioned material combinations is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: 3DP-printed packaging with 15% RK 3087 and a FFF-printed structure with 5% PP 7330

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4 REFERENCES

ASTM D6773-16, (2016). Standard Test Method for Bulk Solids Using Schulze Ring Shear Tester.

Buschbeck S.; Reichelt C.; Rinberg R.; Kroll L; Germer, T. (2020). Natural Resin meets Bio-Polyester. Bioplastics MAGAZINE, vol. 15; issue 03, pp. 28-30.

EN ISO 3953. 2011-01-31: Metallic powders — Determination of tap density.

EN ISO 60. 1999-04-16: Plastics - Determination of apparent density of material that can be poured from a specified funnel.

Jerman M.; Krinke S.; Kühnel L.; Müller M.; Valentinčič J.; Zeidler H. (2020). Additive manufacturing using renewable materials: concept of upcycling peach kernels for use in Binder Jetting and FFF. Proceedings of euspen's 20th International Conference & Exhibition, Pages 123-124, ISBN 978-0-9957751-7-6.

Zeidler H.; Klemm D.; Böttger-Hiller F.; Fritsch S.; Joo Le Guen M. Singamneni S. (2018). 3D printing of biodegradable parts using renewable biobased materials, Procedia Manufacturing, Volume 21, pp 117-124, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2018.02.101>.